

ANALYSIS OF FRACTURE FEATURES OF CARBON FIBRE
REINFORCED ZINC BASE ALLOY COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

A carbon fibre reinforced zinc base alloy composite has been fabricated with the liquid-infiltration method. The features of tensile and impact fractures were studied by means of scanning electron microscopy and electron probe analyzer. The results indicated that the interfacial bonding between the fibre and zinc or zinc alloy is poor as a great deal of fibre pullout on the fracture surface. The failure of the composite was controlled by the cleavage fracture of the matrixes. It was concluded that the toughness of matrixes and the fibre/matrix bond force influence the fracture behaviour of composites.

INTRODUCTION

Elliot F. Olster et al [1] has reported that when the crack propagates across the filaments in fibre reinforced composites the toughness increases in proportion to the debonding of the interface. In this opinion, a weak interface is desirable for increased toughness. However, in the case of graphite/nickel composite, the presence of a weak interface did not result in a good impact resistance, as was found for instance with the interface in silica fibre reinforced aluminium [2]. Although it gives rise to much more amount of fibre pullout where the frictional forces and the pullout length control the toughness, a weaker bonding makes it poor the attribution of matrixes to the toughness of composite materials.

The present work was undertaken with the purpose of observing the fracture behaviour of carbon fibre reinforced zinc base alloy and also exploring some of the fractures with the aid of the scanning electron microscope and electron probe analyzer. Industrial pure zinc and zinc alloy (4% Al, 1% Cu, 0.05% Mg) were used as matrix alloys. The fibre was 7 μm in

diametre, and its typical value of the ultimate tensile strength was 2940 N/mm². The surface of the fibre was coated with nickel by electroless deposition. The composite was prepared by infiltration of carbon fibres with melting zinc or its alloy.

OBSERVATION OF FRACTURE FEATURES

1. Tensile Fracture

The pictures of tensile fracture surface are shown in Fig. 1a-b and show a typical example of fibre pullout, which indicates that the fibre/matrix bond strength was low. The majority of the fibres shows fractures initiating from internal defects, generally at the highly stressed core. The crack propagated through the matrixes along the cleavage planes.

2. Impact Fracture

Visual examination of impact bonding fracture surfaces indicated a different fracture mode of the pure zinc and its alloy compared to their composite materials. The macrofracture surface of the pure zinc appeared metallic luster and that of the composite grey. The cleavage planes of the pure zinc was very large (shown in Fig. 2a).

In general, the impact bending fracture has same characteristics as the longitudinal tensile fracture, i.e. a great deal of fibre pullout and cleavage fracture in matrix. The composites (zinc or zinc alloy base) will fail by multiple cracking of the matrix, followed by failure of the carbon fibres. The fibres may affect the solidification process of the metal matrixes and change their microstructures (Fig. 2b).

a. b.
Figure 1. Tensile fracture surface of the composite.

a. Cleavage planes of the pure zinc b. Impact fracture surface of zinc composite

Figure 2.

DISCUSSION

The pure zinc and zinc alloy used were brittle and poor in plasticity. It was easy to induce stress concentrations in the brittle matrixes. For longitudinal tensile loading, the cracks began to propagate. After some cracks reached the interface of the fibre matrix, their subsequent propagation was controlled by interfacial bond force.

The thermal coefficients of expansion of the carbon fibre and zinc alloy are $(-0.1-0.23) \times 10^{-6}/\text{C}^{\circ}$, $26 \times 10^{-6}/\text{C}^{\circ}$ respectively. Because of the differing thermal expansions or contractions of the fibre and the matrix thermally induced stresses are produced on cooling from the manufactural temperature [3]. The residual stresses will cause debonding at the interface.

The interface of the carbon fibre -- zinc or zinc alloy was investigated by means of electron probe analyzer. It was found that the nickel coated diffused into the matrix (Fig. 3). This may improve the wettability of the fibre to the matrixes. However, the dissolution of nickel in zinc gave rise to a new phase around the carbon fibre (Fig. 4). This intermediate phase increased brittleness and could degrade the tensile strength of zinc base composite. Further work is processing.

A great deal fibre pullout indicated that the bond between the fibre and zinc or zinc alloy matrix was poor. Thus when the crack arrived at the interface, higher stresses at the tip of the crack resulted in the debonding

Figure 3. A diffused layer in nickel between the graphite and the matrix.

Figure 4. A intermediate phase around carbon fibres in zinc composite.

of the fibre so that the crack propagated along the interface till the fracture of fibre at the weakest section. Simultaneously, other cracks in the matrixes propagated and connected along their cleavage planes, leading to the failure of the composite.

CONCLUSIONS

- a. In order to improve fracture features of the composite, a good interfacial bonding is necessary.
- b. From whole fracture surface, the cleavage fracture of the matrixes controlled the failure of the composite. Thus improvements of the properties of the matrixes are also essential.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank Mr. Song Ruihong, Miss Wang Haimong for their work on the observation of SEM fractography.

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